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Article

When Technology Meets Sustainability: Microplastic Removal from Industrial Wastewater, Including Impact Analysis and Life Cycle Assessment

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Abstract: Microplastics (MPs) that are ubiquitous in aquatic environments and industrial wastewater streams have been identified as key hotspots of MP contamination. It is significantly more effective to remove MPs at these points before they enter municipal wastewater streams. This study is an environmental assessment of a novel pilot plant for the removal of MPs and the chemical oxygen demand (COD) from wastewater with a high MP contamination from a plastics manufacturer in Germany. MP removal is based on physical–chemical agglomeration–fixation by organosilanes. Formed agglomerates are separated using a belt filter. The COD is removed by an adsorption process. The resulting MP removal was $98.0 \pm 1.1\%$ by mass and $99.9987 \pm 0.0007\%$ by particle count, while the COD was reduced by $96 \pm 2.7\%$. The system’s sustainability is evaluated using the Life Cycle Assessment methodology, evaluating system construction, operation, and end-of-life considerations. The current pilot plant is also compared to an optimized circular and sustainable upgrade, where drivers of environmental burdens are eliminated and collected MPs are reused. Significant reductions in environmental impact categories are achieved and the global warming potential is reduced by 96%. This study provides a sustainability assessment of a novel technology and circular solution to remove MPs from highly polluted industrial wastewater.

Keywords: microplastics; life cycle assessment; impact analysis; removal technology; sustainable process design; carbon footprint; water quality; circular economy

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1. Introduction

Microplastic (MP) research in the last two decades has revealed that MPs are one of the biggest environmental problems and challenges in modern water and wastewater treatment [1]. A particular problem is their high persistence in the environment, resulting in slow degradation rates and constant fragmentation into even smaller MPs [2]. This leads to constantly increasing pollution levels and puts more and more stress on aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems [3]. Further, current research shows that they are not only an environmental pollutant, but are also of concern for human health [4], due to the transfer from the environment to humans or human exposure to various plastic products, with numerous studies showing potential negative impacts [5].

Treated wastewater effluent is one of the main point sources of MPs in the environment. While it is estimated that wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) remove 80–99% of MPs from wastewater, numerous studies show that WWTP effluent still has high MP levels due

to the high volumes of wastewater being treated [6], and the extreme MP contamination in the inflowing wastewater [7].

Industrial wastewater, particularly from plastic production, manufacturing, or recycling industries, is often highly polluted with MPs and high levels of oxidizable organic matter, which creates a high chemical oxygen demand (COD) [8]. The presence of industrial wastewater in municipal WWTPs imposes a substantial burden due to the MP load [9].

To avoid plastic emissions into the environment, to allow the reuse of wastewater, which is essential in regions facing water scarcity, and to build sustainable processes based on circular economy approaches [10], efficient methods for the removal of MPs and COD from water are needed [11]. The biggest challenge is finding a robust, sustainable, and economical removal method with low operational costs and maintenance requirements, as described in Table 1 for commonly discussed potential solutions for MP removal [12].

Table 1. Evaluation of known particle (MP) removal technologies.

Technology	Evaluation	Reference
Membrane filtration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High operational costs due to extensive scaling and fouling; • High energy needs and high investment costs. 	[12,13]
Dissolved air flotation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited effectiveness in case studies; • Suffer from a high energy demand. 	[14]
Coagulation and flocculation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applicable with low technical effort and a low energy demand, resulting in low costs; • Commercially available flocculants are highly sensitive to water composition and polymer types resulting in a low level of robustness in relation to fluctuations; • Limited applicability. 	[15–17]

The present study shows the application of a novel class of agglomeration–fixation reagents based on organosilanes, applied in the context of industrial wastewater from a plastic manufacturing facility. The organosilanes attach to the MPs suspended in the water, collect them in large agglomerates, and chemically fix them in a water-induced sol–gel process [18,19]. The chemical composition of the organosilanes can be specifically adapted to the plastic types contained in the water, whereby the interaction between the organosilane and the plastic surface is decisive [20,21].

To design truly sustainable water and wastewater treatment processes, it is essential to compare the environmental impacts caused by their production and operation with the ecological benefits they provide through wastewater treatment [22,23]. The concept of sustainable process design within planetary boundaries is becoming increasingly important from economic, ecologic, and societal perspectives [24,25]. Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) stand out as strong tools for measuring the overall environmental advantages stemming from enhanced wastewater treatment systems [26], employing a thorough and systematic approach, considering the complete life cycle of a technology, product, or process—from raw material extraction through manufacturing, usage, and eventual disposal. LCAs are adaptable and can be customized to suit specific regional contexts, a valuable feature given the variations in wastewater management strategies and energy production practices among countries [27].

Evaluations of wastewater treatment technologies on a life cycle basis have been the focus of several research studies. This research has focused on areas such as optimization strategies, development of new technologies, and infrastructural planning. An overall

review of LCA studies related to municipal wastewater management systems showed that while the method has been used for evaluating various WWTP upgrades or trade-offs, there are also challenges and limitations related to end-of-life considerations within the boundaries of LCA evaluations [26].

MP release and their effects on the environment have also been a frequent topic of research. However, LCA studies have been very limited in applying quantifiable ecosystem impacts based on the life cycle of MP waste, particularly due to the lack of accurate inventory data and characterization factors [28]. This study proposes a novel approach by integrating LCA methodology with recently developed characterization factors from the MariLCA project [29]. This integration enables the consideration of both the benefits of waste reuse and the final impacts on the ecosystem by discharged MPs, fully addressing the end-of-life implications of MP waste treatment. In this way, this paper represents a novel assessment through its comprehensive LCA evaluation of an existing highly efficient system and comparison to an optimized scenario for continuous MP and COD removal.

This paper investigates a practical case study of industrial wastewater treatment scenarios based on wastewater from a plastic manufacturer in Germany. It evaluates the environmental impacts associated with the implementation of a pilot system for MP and COD removal, which is based on physicochemical agglomeration–fixation using organosilanes followed by COD removal by adsorption. The assessment considers the environmental impacts across the complete life cycle of the treated wastewater, from its entry to the treatment system to the disposal of all waste streams. This is followed by a comparative assessment of the currently operational pilot plant and an optimized scenario with a sustainable upgrade, with the aim of determining the benefits of eliminating key drivers of environmental burdens and incorporating waste reuse schemes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Evaluation of Outlined Scenarios

This study proposes three distinct scenarios: In the first scenario, the industrial wastewater remains untreated and flows to the municipal WWTP. In this case, up to 90% of MPs may still eventually be removed from the wastewater through the municipal WWTP processes, however, due to high volumes of wastewater being processed and released into the environment, a significant amount of MPs enter the environment, as indicated by statistical studies of MP retention in conventional WWTPs [30]. The estimation was made that 10% of MPs will end up in the environment despite retention by the municipal WWTP. In this scenario, there are also no benefits regarding water reuse and the potential reuse of solid waste.

In the second scenario, the pilot plant is proposed as an implementation, allowing the retention of MPs, reduction of COD, and water reuse. The existing pilot system is considered in this scenario, where the treatment is carried out in batches and where generated agglomerates are separated using an incline filter device with a consumable filter fleece. In this scenario, the dried agglomerates, as solid waste, are assumed to be incinerated, as this is currently the main practice for MP waste treatment other than landfilling [31].

The third scenario proposes an optimized circular system, where the operation is shifted from a batch system to a continuous system, including the use of an endless belt filter for the separation of agglomerates. The proposed optimized system displays the benefits of reducing the consumption of filter fleece, as well as the closed-loop treatment of the final solid waste, providing a holistic solution system for industrial application.

Data for the 1st and 2nd scenarios were obtained through pilot testing. The differences in MP and COD release, amount of retained solid waste, and water reuse were based on

the tested pilot plant and wastewater from an industrial plastic manufacturing facility. Material and energy consumption data used for the LCA evaluation were likewise based on designs and measurements for the pilot device, while data for solid waste treatment via incineration were based on average data for Germany.

Regarding the 3rd scenario, which proposes an optimized continuous process for wastewater treatment and solid waste reuse, data were developed based on the pilot plant's capabilities for MP removal from the 2nd scenario. Additional data on the use of filter fleece use, using an endless belt filter were based on information from industrial separator providers [32].

The results are presented as a comparison of parameters related to both the device performance for MP and COD removal, as well as water reuse and the environmental impacts of the pilot device and the optimized device.

2.2. Pilot Plant Operation

The Wasser 3.0 PE-X[®] pilot plant is a mobile wastewater treatment unit that targets the removal of MPs by agglomeration–fixation and the reduction of the COD by adsorption [8] (Figure 1). In the first step, agglomeration–fixation, the wastewater from the plastic grinding process is filled in a 200 L tank with a mechanical mixer. After filling the tank and starting the stirring process, 250 mL of agglomeration reagent (abcr eco Wasser 3.0 PE-X[®], wastewater; AB930003, abcr.com/de_en/ab930003 (accessed on 23 January 2025), abcr GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) is added using a dosing pump. Subsequently, the agglomeration–fixation process begins, in which MPs are collected in agglomerates through a physical interaction with the agglomeration reagent and the MP surface [33]. Subsequently, the agglomerates are fixed in a chemical, water-induced reaction of the agglomeration reagent, which gives them high stability [34].

Figure 1. Pilot plant scheme, including sampling points.

The formed MP agglomerates are separated from the water by a belt filter with a filter fleece (FIV12-1067, Leiblein GmbH, Hardheim, Germany, material: polyester, pore size: 70–80 μm).

For the last treatment step, the COD reduction unit, a 250 L fixed bed reactor containing 175 L of granulated activated carbon (GAC) (AquaSorb[™] 2000 by Jacobi Carbons, Premnitz, Germany) is used, with a contact time of 10 min. In this case study, the goal was to reduce the COD below 1000 mg/L to comply with municipal and federal regulations [35,36] for the discharge of wastewater and to avoid additional wastewater fees [37].

The pilot plant is operated at the Wasser 3.0 Research Center in Landau, Germany. For the experiments, two Intermediate Bulk Containers (IBCs) containing 1 m³ of raw wastewater from a medium-sized plastic manufacturer, a full-service provider for the grinding and refinement of plastic products, were shipped to the Wasser 3.0 Research Center, where they were treated and analyzed.

2.2.1. Test Phases and Sampling

The pilot-scale plant is operated semi-continuously in 200 L batches. Thus, each IBC containing 1 m³ results in five 200 L batches, which are processed in a fully automated manner. Samples of each batch were taken at three different locations: 1st—untreated wastewater, 2nd—after the belt filter, and 3rd—after the COD reduction unit. This resulted in 5 samples per IBC and respective sample locations.

2.2.2. Analyses

All samples were analyzed for pH value, COD (DIN ISO 15705-H45) [38], particle count, total suspended solids (TSSs, DIN 38 409-H2-2) [39], and turbidity (DIN EN ISO 7027) [40].

pH Value

To measure the pH value, the table pH meter pH 50 VioLab Set was used (Dostmann electronic GmbH, Wertheim-Reicholzheim, Germany).

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

The COD was measured using Macherey Nagel's tube test nanocolor COD 40-15000. The spectrophotometer Nanocolor UV/VIS II and the thermoblock Nanocolor Vario C2 were used (Machery-Nagel GmbH & Co. KG, Düren, Germany). The procedure complies with DIN ISO 15705-H45.

Particle Count of MPs

As the wastewater originates from the industrial plastic grinding process, it can be presumed that all particles within the wastewater are MPs. In this industrial process, fresh tap water is used for the plastic grinding process and the particles introduced in the water are the residues from plastic grinding. Because there are only plastic particles contained in the wastewater, simple particle counting can be applied to determine the MP concentration and no complex MP analytics are necessary.

Particle counting was performed by filtration of a subsample onto a membrane filter followed by optical counting under a microscope. For the filtration step, 100 mL of sample or diluted sample were filtered onto a white round membrane filter with grid (pore size: 0.45 µm, Ø47 mm, Cytiva Whatmann, Global Lifescience Solutions Operations UK Ltd., Amersham, UK) using vacuum filtration. To avoid clogging of the filter and prevent the overlapping of the particles, which would result in miscounting, highly contaminated samples were diluted with demineralized water up to a ratio of 1:100. After filtration, the membrane filter is stored in a labeled petri dish and inspected under a ZEISS Axio Zoom.V16 microscope with Zen Blue Software Zen Blue 3.8 (Carl Zeiss Microscopy Deutschland GmbH, Oberkochen, Deutschland). The microscope is equipped with an Axiocam 105 color R2 and PlanNeoFluar Z 1x/0.25 objective, resulting in a resolution of 1 µm/pixel. For each filter, photos of 5 squares were taken and the particles were counted manually. The particle count was extrapolated to particles/L by the total surface area of the filter and the filtered water volume.

Total Suspended Solids—MPs by Weight

It is presumed that all particles in the wastewater are MPs originating from the industrial plastic grinding process, thus another way to determine the level of MP contamination is to measure the particle weight.

The quantitative determination of the total suspended solids (TSSs) was based on DIN 38 409-H2-2. Round filters of 125 mm (MN 640w, retention capacity 7–12 µm, Machery-Nagel GmbH & Co. KG, Düren, Germany) were used in a vacuum filtration process. The

filters were first flushed with 100 mL of demineralized water and dried for 3 h at 105 °C. The dry, empty filters were subsequently weighed. After weighing, 1 L of the sample was filtered, and the filters were dried again for 3 h at 105 °C and subsequently weighed. The weight difference between the full and empty filters results in the TSSs.

Turbidity

The turbidity was measured using the spectrophotometer Nanocolor UV/VIS II from Macherey Nagel, according to DIN EN ISO 7027. A total of 10 mL of sample were pipetted into empty tubes with an outer diameter of 16 mm (reaction tubes 16 mm OD, item number 91,680, Machery-Nagel GmbH & Co. KG, Düren, Germany). The tube was shaken until homogeneous, then placed and measured in the spectrophotometer.

Agglomerate Treatment

The agglomerates removed in each test run were collected in a stainless-steel container and, after each batch, transferred to a 5 L glass beaker. To determine the dry weight and the water content, the agglomerates were dried for 3 h at 105 °C in a drying oven.

2.3. LCA Methodology

LCA stands out as a preferred method for assessing environmental impacts due to its diverse benefits, enabling the consideration of variations in energy sources and materials, as well as temporal and geographical variations. In this study, the advanced wastewater treatment system operating at a pilot scale is evaluated.

Pre-screening of the environmental impacts of the process indicated that the dominant contribution towards overall environmental burdens is generated by polyester fleece used for separation filters, which prompted the design of a pilot plant solution that did not consume large amounts of fleece for the removal of agglomerates and offered a sustainable system for further optimization.

The environmental evaluation was conducted as a comparative analysis, where the reduction of impacts following the elimination of the belt filter was depicted. The evaluated scenarios are described in detail in Section 2.1. To conduct the environmental assessment, OpenLCA 2.0 software [41] with the integrated Ecoinvent 3.9 database [42] was used.

To complement the LCAs of the systems' construction and operation with the environmental life cycle effects of retained MPs, the innovative MP characterization model developed by the MarILCA project [29] was used. The calculation model enables the quantification of physical effects on biota, based on total MP mass released into either freshwater or saltwater and taking into consideration the size, shape, and polymer type of MPs. Further details on the calculation of MP impacts on the environment are available in Section 3.4.

3. Environmental Impact Assessment Framework

3.1. Goals and Scope

The functional unit in this study, for which all the potential environmental impacts were calculated, was represented by 1 m³ of treated wastewater using the proposed systems. To allocate the impacts, the total lifetime of the treatment setup was assumed to be 30 years, considering that 2000 m³ of wastewater can be treated annually using the semi-continuous system. The boundaries of the studied systems were set to model a cradle-to-grave life cycle when considering the treated wastewater, where relevant mass and energy, as well as treatment of wastewater and solid waste, were included within the boundaries. The processes contained within the system boundaries were evaluated according to the cradle-

to-gate principle to focus on the upstream effects of the device construction and operation. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the system boundaries.

Figure 2. System boundaries for LCA evaluation.

3.2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The data used for the LCI were calculated based on the defined system boundaries and technical data provided by the pilot tests. The functional unit was considered when calculating the inventory data, where the flow amounts were converted to the functional unit of 1 m³ of treated wastewater.

The pilot plant unit, considered as the combination of the MP removal unit, the belt filter, and the COD reduction unit, is constructed from a total of 2780.5 kg of steel, 560 kg of which is stainless steel, while the remainder is unalloyed steel. The manufacturing of the units from raw steel sheets requires a total of 320 h of mechanical labor, which is divided between 160 h of laser cutting and 160 h of arc welding. The laser-cutting process was modeled with a representative dataset in the Ecoinvent 3.9 database. The dataset for welding is based on weld length, where the modeling assumed a welding speed of 2.4 m/h [43], from which the total length of the weld was calculated. The German electricity mix was used to model electricity demand in both the laser cutting and the arc welding processes.

The standard IBC reservoir, with a volume of 1000 L, is constructed from a polypropylene inner tank weighing 14.5 kg and a low-alloyed steel pallet weighing 42 kg [44]. The stirrer for the reservoir (PROMI CON 140) is a unit constructed from 20 kg of stainless steel [45].

The setup contains a compressor and two pumps to provide the initial flow of wastewater and to transfer water between process sections. To obtain accurate mass input data for pump units, an estimation was made using a bill of materials for a representative pump, which was adjusted based on pump size. The representative pump's detailed bill of materials states that it consists of 5.70 kg of cast iron, 0.67 kg of polystyrene, 6.42 kg of steel, and 0.60 kg of aluminum for a total mass of 13.39 kg [46]. The pumps (Grundfos Unilift CC5-A1), weighing a total of 20.5 kg [47], were modeled with mass inputs based on these specifications and adjusted for size. An estimation for the compressor was made using the same methodology, where a representative Ecoinvent 3.9 dataset for a compressor pro-

duction process was selected and adjusted for size, with the compressor (Aerotec Zenith) weighing a total of 30.5 kg and the representative compressor in the dataset weighing 139.3 kg. In this way, the study estimated the actual size of the compressor used at the pilot plant.

The electricity demand of the MP removal system was determined using an electric power meter and considered the fixed setup of the reactor, the outlet pump, and the incline belt filter. The total electricity demand of this setup was measured as 0.8 kWh per m³ of treated wastewater. The incline belt filter itself has a nominal power of 0.12 kW and is used for 30 min during the 1 h timeframe of batch treatment, resulting in a total of 0.06 kWh/m³ electricity use for the belt filter and 0.74 kWh/m³ electricity use for the combined reactor and outlet pump. In the optimized circular model, an endless belt filter device is used instead of the incline belt filter, which has a higher nominal power at 0.36 kW and thus uses 0.18 kWh/m³ of electricity per m³ of treated wastewater. The nominal power of the belt filter devices was obtained from custom-made products utilized at the pilot plant. The electricity demands of the compressor and feed pump, which are used to provide the initial flow of wastewater, were calculated through their nominal power, which is 1.50 kW for the compressor and 1.67 kW for the pump. The time of operation during the 1 h timeframe is 5.5 min, which results in a total electricity consumption of 0.14 kWh/m³ for the compressor and 0.15 kWh/m³ for the feed pump. All electricity consumption was modeled with consideration of the German electricity mix.

The use of organosilanes, which form the agglomeration reagent described in Section 2.2: Pilot plant operation, was measured at 1.00 mL of pure organosilane solution dosed per m³ treated wastewater. The organosilanes were modeled using the Ecoinvent 3.9-specific dataset for tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) production, which represents an estimate of the organosilane mixture. While organosilanes represent a large group of chemical substances, TEOS is a close approximation of the reagent organosilane utilized in the experiments because of its chemical similarity. The volume was recalculated into mass units by considering the density of TEOS at 940 kg/m³ [48].

The consumption of belt filter fleece was measured at 18.35 m per m³ of treated wastewater. The fleece was modeled as polyester cloth, where its mass was calculated by considering fleece width of 0.5 m and thickness of 0.038 m [49], as well as the density of polyester at 1380 kg/m³. A total of 4.81 kg belt filter fleece is used per m³ of treated wastewater in the pilot plant scenario. In the optimized circular model, the incline belt filter is assumed to be replaced by an endless belt filter, a device that operates continuously and performs self-cleaning while separating solid waste from water. The total length of the fleece on the endless belt filter, which is replaced annually, is 9.3 m [32]. When accounting for the annual volume of 2000 m³ of treated wastewater, the total amount of fleece required in the optimized scenario is only 0.47 cm per m³ of wastewater.

The COD reduction unit operation requires a 175 L batch of GAC, which is replaced annually. This amount of GAC was allocated according to the assumption that 2000 m³ of wastewater is treated annually. By considering a GAC density of 500 kg/m³, an allocated amount of 0.044 kg of GAC was calculated for 1 m³ of treated wastewater.

The pilot plant scenario assumes that the final separated and dried solid waste is incinerated. To avoid disclosing data from the plastic manufacturer, an incineration process of waste polyethylene terephthalate was used as an estimation. The incineration process of plastic waste itself brings both burdens and benefits in terms of environmental impacts, where the benefits of energy recovery are often outweighed by the generated emissions, as shown by the LCA results reported in previous works [50]. The benefits in this scenario were modeled on the assumption of energy recovery for electricity production at an efficiency of

35% while replacing the German electricity mix, which is in large part comprised of fossil sources, such as coal and natural gas [51].

In the optimized circular model scenario, the solid waste is assumed to be reused through a circular economy concept, where dried agglomerates are applied as a filler in concrete mixtures. Fillers are often used in concrete to densify and homogenize the cement paste, providing a beneficial effect on concrete in both fresh and hardened states [52]. This reuse strategy enables the extension of the MP waste life cycle while reducing the need for raw materials that would otherwise be used as fillers. One of the most common filler additives used when preparing concrete mixes is quartz or silica sand, which improves the mechanical performance of concrete. However, its production requires the extraction of raw materials through mining and quarrying operations [53]. By utilizing waste agglomerates as a replacement for silica sand, the strategy provided an unburdening effect, which was evaluated by assuming a negative value for silica sand in LCA modeling. The Ecoinvent 3.9 process for silica sand with a SiO₂ (quartz) content of over 85% was used to model the production process. In this way, the study considers the treatment of solid waste from the system through two different scenarios. As there are no direct gaseous emissions coming from the system, gas outputs are considered only within the background processes of the LCA model.

As both processes use GAC treatment to remove the COD from wastewater, the final COD load is considered as an output of the process, amounting to a total of 0.33 kg per m³ of wastewater. Finally, the reuse of purified water for industrial purposes is considered to avoid the production of additional freshwater. Avoided production of 0.9 m³ water per m³ wastewater is considered in both cases. The Ecoinvent 3.9 process used in this case represented an average production of water from underground water with chemical treatments, including pumping from an aquifer, chemical enhancement, and pressurization for distribution.

Table 2 shows the material and energy flows for the wastewater treatment systems, considering the base case with the current pilot plant scenario and the alternative case with the optimized circular model. All the flow amounts have been calculated to reflect the functional unit. The calculations related to end-of-life treatment and avoidance of waste are explained in detail in Section 4.1: Pilot trials.

Table 2. Life cycle inventory for the wastewater treatment system.

System Element	Parameter	Amount (Pilot Plant)	Amount (Optimized Circular Model)	Unit
Device construction elements				
Pilot plant material	Stainless steel	9.33×10^{-3}	9.33×10^{-3}	kg
	Unalloyed steel	3.70×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-2}	kg
Pilot plant construction	Laser cutting	2.67×10^{-3}	2.67×10^{-3}	h
	Arc welding	6.40×10^{-3}	6.40×10^{-3}	m
IBC reservoir	Low-alloyed steel	7.00×10^{-4}	7.00×10^{-4}	kg
	Polypropylene tank	2.42×10^{-4}	2.42×10^{-4}	kg
Stirrer	Stainless steel	3.33×10^{-4}	3.33×10^{-4}	kg
Compressor	Compressor unit	3.65×10^{-6}	3.65×10^{-6}	Items
Feed pump	Reference pump [46]	5.00×10^{-5}	5.00×10^{-5}	Items
Outlet pump	Reference pump [46]	5.00×10^{-5}	5.00×10^{-5}	Items

Table 2. Cont.

System Element	Parameter	Amount (Pilot Plant)	Amount (Optimized Circular Model)	Unit
Operation and consumable materials				
Electricity use—compressor	Electricity	0.14	0.14	kWh
Electricity use—feed pump	Electricity	0.15	0.15	kWh
Electricity use—reactor tank	Electricity	0.74	0.74	kWh
Electricity use—filtration separator	Electricity	0.06	0.18	kWh
Organosilanes	Tetraethylorthosilicate	9.40×10^{-4}	9.40×10^{-4}	kg
Belt filter fleece	Polyester cloth	4.81	1.22×10^{-3}	kg
Absorber material	GAC	4.38×10^{-2}	4.38×10^{-2}	kg
End-of-life treatment and reuse of waste				
COD load	COD	0.33	0.33	kg
Incineration of agglomerates and energy recovery	Incinerated plastic waste	4.30	/	kg
	Electricity production (unburdening)	−10.09	/	kWh
Water reuse	Water production (unburdening)	−0.90	−0.90	m ³
Agglomerate reuse	Silica sand (unburdening)	/	−4.30	kg
Treated wastewater	Reference flow	1.00	1.00	m ³

3.3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

To calculate environmental impacts, the CML method was chosen, as it is one of the most frequently used methods for calculating impact categories at the midpoint level. The environmental impact results are expressed with eleven different impact categories or indicators, where the following potentials are included: abiotic depletion of fossil fuels and minerals, acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity of freshwater, marine water, and earth systems, human toxicity, ozone depletion, photochemical oxidation, and global warming. All considered impact categories are measured in the units shown in Table 6.

3.4. LCA-Based Evaluation of MPs Released into the Environment

The impacts of MP effects on the environment were evaluated based on specific data for MP release in the wastewater of the evaluated process, which were collected according to the MarILCA framework. The methodology enables the calculation of characterization factors for emissions of different MPs to different environmental compartments while evaluating their physical effects on biota and consequent damage to ecosystem quality. The calculations are made using specifically defined data for the discharge compartment, polymer type, MP shape, and MP size class. The comparative unit in which the physical effects of MPs on biota are measured expresses the potentially affected fraction of species (PAFs) integrated over time and the volume of the freshwater compartment, per unit of mass of the chemical emitted. In practice, the impacts are expressed in units of PAFs m³ day/kg_{emitted}.

Due to the location of the plastic producer in Germany, the discharge compartment was defined as freshwater. The MP shape was defined as unspecified fragments, as the MPs are released from the plastic grinding process. The MP size class was based on a weighted average of size class data provided in Table 3, where the highest percentage of MPs was in the 10 µm class.

The specific polymer type was excluded from the modeling in order to protect the data of the plastic manufacturer. This means that the final characterization factor figure is

calculated as an average of the available polymer types. The data were used to calculate a final characterization factor of 4.05×10^{-6} PAFs $\text{m}^3 \text{ day/kg}$.

Table 3. Size class distribution and characterization factors of released MPs.

Size Class	Average Characterization Factor (PAFs $\text{m}^3 \text{ Day/kg}_{\text{emitted}}$)	Share of MPs
10 μm	1.33×10^6	54%
100 μm	4.91×10^6	37%
1000 μm	1.69×10^7	9%
Weighted average:	4.05×10^6	100%

This factor was multiplied by the mass of MPs released to the environment under the assumption that the wastewater first flows from the industrial plant to the municipal WWTP, where 90% of MPs are retained. The final impact, which measures physical impacts on biota by MPs, is expressed in units of PAFs $\text{m}^3 \text{ day/m}^3$ treated wastewater.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Pilot Trials

4.1.1. Measured Removal Performance

In the pilot trials, two IBCs with highly contaminated water from the industrial effluent were treated and analyzed for the COD, TSSs, particle count, and turbidity (Figure 3). The initial COD was 8450 ± 743 mg/L and 9940 ± 1509 mg/L for IBC 1 and IBC 2, respectively. After the treatment, for IBC 1, the COD was 539 ± 86 mg/L, leading to a removal of 93.6%, while for IBC 2, a more efficient removal of 98%, resulting in a COD of 170 ± 28 mg/L, was reached. The average COD removal was $96 \pm 2.7\%$.

The particle counts were 282 ± 23 billion particles/L and 119 ± 15 billion particles/L for IBC 1 and IBC 2, respectively. Following treatment, they were reduced to 5.2 ± 0.8 million particles/L for IBC 1 and to 1.1 ± 0.8 million particles/L for IBC 2. This results in a $99.9987 \pm 0.0007\%$ removal by particle count.

The initial TSSs were 6532 ± 152 mg/L and 3825 ± 671 mg/L for IBC 1 and IBC 2, respectively. After the treatment, the TSSs were 10 ± 5 mg/L for IBC 1 and 25 ± 13 mg/L for IBC 2, with an average MP removal (given by TSSs) of $98.0 \pm 1.1\%$.

The turbidity was reduced from an average of 3437 ± 596 NTU to 15 ± 5 NTU or by $99.6 \pm 0.1\%$. A previously performed pilot study showed a strong correlation between turbidity, TSSs, and particle count, making it a good indicative parameter as a process control [8]. The pH increased from 4.9 ± 0.3 before the treatment, which is slightly acidic, to a neutral value of 6.7 ± 0.3 , which was caused by the two-stage treatment process.

The TSSs and particle count of the untreated wastewater were considerably higher than in previous pilot trials with wastewater from the same company [8]. The TSSs in the previous pilot trials ranged from 411 mg/L to 2381 mg/L, with an average of 1068 ± 456 mg/L compared to an average TSSs of 5024 ± 1435 mg/L in the presented trials. Previous trials showed a particle count of $48 \text{ million} \pm 28 \text{ million}$ particles/L, ranging from 10 million to 125 million particles/L. The particle contamination in the presented trials had a mean of 192 ± 82 billion particles/L—an average of 4000 times higher. Besides the higher contamination of the wastewater, the main reason for the increase is that the particle count was strongly influenced using a more advanced microscope for the particle counting in the presented study. The higher optical resolution and better illumination enabled the detection of smaller particles and more reliable identification of particles. The presented results are shown graphically in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Results of the trials with the pilot plant, for IBC 1, IBC 2, and the mean. Presented are the TSSs, particle count, COD, turbidity, and pH.

The comparison of the removal performance in both pilot studies (Table 4) demonstrates an improved removal performance for MPs, TSSs, particle count, and turbidity, as well as improved COD removal by the new pilot plant. The higher contamination of the untreated wastewater does not pose a problem for the process, which can efficiently remove MPs and the COD.

Table 4. Comparison of the performance of the previous pilot trials from Sturm et al., 2024 [8], to the new pilot trials of the here presented study.

Parameter	New Pilot Trials	Previous Pilot Trials
TSSs removal (%)	98.0 ± 1.1	94.6 ± 3.9
Particle removal (%)	100.0	97.92 ± 2.31
COD removal (%)	96 ± 2.7	94.3 ± 8.9
Turbidity removal (%)	99.6 ± 0.1	98.3 ± 1.3

4.1.2. Extrapolation of the Removal Performance

Using the measured removal performance, wastewater streams of the piloted company, and assumptions in Table S1 in the Supplementary Materials, the removal performance can be extrapolated on a daily and yearly basis. The extrapolation of these parameters leads to the results depicted in Table 5.

Table 5. Extrapolation of the removal performance, material, and energy consumption per day and year.

	Per m ³	Per day	Per year
Outputs			
Rinsed wastewater	1 m ³	8 m ³	2000 m ³
Removed MPs (TSSs)	5.1 kg	40.8 kg	10.2 t
Removed MPs (particles)	201 trillion (10 ¹²)	1.6 quadrillion (10 ¹⁵)	2.6 quintillion (10 ¹⁸)
Removed COD load	8.8 kg	70.7 kg	17.7 t
Rinsed wastewater	1 m ³	8 m ³	2000 m ³
Inputs			
Energy consumption	0.8 kWh	6.4 kWh	1600 kWh
Organosilane mix consumption (diluted)	1.25 L	10 L	2500 L
Organosilane mix consumption (pure)	1 mL	8 mL	2 L
Filter fleece consumption	18.35 m	146.8 m	36.7 km
Agglomerate generation			
Wet agglomerates	20.0 kg	160 kg	40 t
Water content		77.3%	

The results show that over one year, 2000 m³ of wastewater are treated, and 10.2 t of MPs and 17.7 t of COD are removed. A total of 1600 kWh of electricity, 2 L undiluted PE-X agglomeration reagent, and 36.7 km of filter fleece are consumed annually in the current pilot plant. Over a year, 40 t of wet agglomerates and 9.1 t of dried agglomerates could be recovered, with a water content of 77.3%.

4.2. Environmental Impact Assessment Results

The comparative environmental assessment results for the various impact categories are presented in Table 6. The impact category differences are also shown in Figure 4, which

depicts the relativized results of the impacts. In Figure 4, results set at 100% for each impact category signify the impact value in the base case scenario, while the result for the alternative scenario is shown relative to the original result.

Table 6. LCA impact category results for the wastewater treatment system cases.

Impact Category	Result (Pilot Plant)	Result (Optimized Circular Model)	Unit
Abiotic depletion	8.80×10^{-5}	2.98×10^{-6}	kg Sb eq.
Abiotic depletion of fossil fuels	358.24	11.43	MJ
Acidification	4.43×10^{-2}	3.07×10^{-3}	kg SO ₂ eq.
Eutrophication	2.39×10^{-3}	1.15×10^{-2}	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq.
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	23.49	1.02	kg 1,4-DB eq.
Global warming	25.37	1.03	kg CO ₂ eq.
Human toxicity	16.12	1.58	kg 1,4-DB eq.
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	2.42×10^4	2.12×10^3	kg 1,4-DB eq.
Ozone layer depletion	8.31×10^{-8}	8.11×10^{-9}	kg CFC-11 eq.
Photochemical oxidation	3.78×10^{-3}	1.85×10^{-4}	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq.
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	9.28×10^{-3}	2.00×10^{-3}	kg 1,4-DB eq.

Figure 4. Relativized LCA impact category results.

The results indicate significant reductions in a majority of calculated impacts, with 10 out of the 11 impact categories displaying a reduction ranging from 78% to 97% when considering the optimized circular model relative to the pilot plant scenario. The greatest reduction is noted in the impact category of abiotic depletion of fossil fuels, which is lowered by 96.8% when considering the optimized circular model in comparison to the pilot plant.

The majority of impact reductions are related to the reduction in filter fleece use as a result of continuous operations using the endless belt filter. The pilot plant setup proposes a calculated consumption of 36.7 km of filter fleece when considering 2000 m³ of treated wastewater per year, while the optimized circular model considers an endless belt filter, which consumes a total of 9.3 m of fleece per year when considering an annual replacement of the self-cleaning filter fleece. A more detailed breakdown of the impacts of the systems' construction and operation, including electricity use, GAC, organosilanes, and belt filter

fleece, on the impact of global warming potential per m³ of treated wastewater is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Breakdown of impacts on GWP by different processes in both scenarios.

Process	GWP (kg CO ₂ -eq/m ³)— Pilot Plant	GWP (kg CO ₂ -eq/m ³)— Optimized Circular Model
Electricity use	0.56	0.62
GAC	0.34	0.34
Organosilanes	2.70 × 10 ⁻³	2.70 × 10 ⁻³
Filter fleece	14.79	2.42 × 10 ⁻³
Device construction	0.20	0.20
Incineration emissions	15.26	/
Incineration benefits	-5.80	/
Filler reuse benefits	/	-0.14
Water reuse benefits	-2.92 × 10 ⁻⁴	-2.92 × 10 ⁻⁴

A graphical representation of the results from Table 6 is displayed in Figure 5, where the unburdening effects of energy recovery are outweighed by the burdening effects of both fleece and incineration emissions for the pilot plant scenario, totaling 25.4 kg CO₂ per m³ wastewater. The total reduction in the impacts of filter fleece use when considering the optimized circular model is over 99%, resulting in an impact of 1.0 kg CO₂ per m³ wastewater.

Figure 5. Breakdown of individual process impacts on global warming potential.

The only evaluated impact category where an increase is noted is the potential for eutrophication. This result is influenced by two main factors. The first is that a greater amount of electricity is used when considering the optimized circular model, as the endless belt filter device has triple the energy consumption of the incline filter device, while the total energy consumption of the entire setup is increased by 15%. Electricity, particularly when sourced from the German grid, has a relatively strong impact on eutrophication due to emissions associated with the extraction of lignite.

The second factor is related to the end-of-life of MP waste, as in the pilot plant scenario, incineration of waste is considered. Due to energy recovery and generation of useful electricity, this process brings beneficial unburdening effects which have a strong effect on eutrophication due to the produced electricity. In the optimized circular scenario, unburdening effects on eutrophication are still present, however, the impact is not as significant.

It should be noted that while there is an increase in eutrophication potential when transitioning to the optimized circular model, both scenarios cause significant reductions in eutrophication compared to the status quo, where no treatment is performed. This is due

to the beneficial effects of COD removal, which also influences eutrophication potential. A representation of the process impact breakdown on four of the evaluated impact categories is shown in Figure 6, where the specific impacts on eutrophication can be seen in Figure 6b. A visual breakdown of all evaluated impact categories is available in Figure S1 of the Supplementary Material.

Figure 6. Breakdown of individual process impacts on evaluated impact categories: (a) acidification, (b) eutrophication, (c) freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, and (d) human toxicity.

The breakdown of specific impact category results shows the dominant impact of filter fleece in nearly all evaluated categories, particularly when considering the pilot plant scenario, where fleece consumption contributes a majority of the impacts in almost all categories. The practice of incineration shows particularly burdensome effects in categories related to human toxicity and ecotoxicity, showing that, despite the potential benefits of energy recovery, this type of end-of-life treatment still generates significant emissions. The substitution of incineration with filler reuse in the circular model conversely shows unburdening effects, which are most significant in the case of freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, and further emphasize the possibilities for impact reduction.

4.3. Comparative Evaluation of Scenarios

Table 8 presents the combined results for all three scenarios, encompassing the show-cased MP and COD removal and generation of agglomerates as well as indicators based on LCA evaluation. The results show a clear improvement when transitioning from the pilot plant to the proposed optimized circular model.

Table 8 displays results for MP release, water reuse, and the impact categories obtained through a comparative LCA evaluation including LCA-based results for the impacts of MPs on the environment. As it has been suggested that the COD is reported as an independent impact category when conducting an LCA of wastewater treatment systems [54], the removed COD load as a result of treatment is also presented for the different scenarios.

The COD is also included in the inventory data, as it contributes to the impact category of eutrophication potential.

Table 8. Comparative results for various parameters across all three evaluated scenarios.

Parameter	Scenario #1 (no MP Treatment)	Scenario #2 (Pilot Plant)	Scenario #3 (Optimized Circular Model)
MP release (kg/m ³)	5.20	0.08	0.08
COD load (kg/m ³)	9.20	0.33	0.33
Water reuse potential (m ³ /year)	0.00	1800.00	1800.00
Physical effects of MPs on biota (PAFs m ³ day/m ³ wastewater)	2.11×10^6	3.04×10^4	3.04×10^4
Eutrophication (kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq./m ³)	0.20	2.39×10^{-3}	1.15×10^{-2}
Abiotic depletion (kg Sb eq./m ³)	/	8.80×10^{-5}	2.98×10^{-6}
Abiotic depletion of fossil fuels (MJ/m ³)	/	358.24	11.43
Acidification (kg SO ₂ eq./m ³)	/	4.43×10^{-2}	3.07×10^{-3}
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq./m ³)	/	23.49	1.02
Global warming (kg CO ₂ eq./m ³)	/	25.37	1.03
Human toxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq./m ³)	/	16.12	1.58
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq./m ³)	/	2.42×10^4	2.12×10^3
Ozone layer depletion (kg CFC-11 eq./m ³)	/	8.31×10^{-8}	8.11×10^{-9}
Photochemical oxidation (kg C ₂ H ₄ eq./m ³)	/	3.78×10^{-3}	1.85×10^{-4}
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq./m ³)	/	9.28×10^{-3}	2.00×10^{-3}

The results of the study can be contextualized by roughly comparing them to previously reported results based on LCAs of wastewater treatment methods. A review of scenarios to improve tertiary treatment in developing countries showed that water reuse, as a result of additional treatment stages, had benefits in terms of environmental impacts, where the GWP was reduced by 0.046 kg CO₂/m³ in treated wastewater as a result of avoided impacts of tap water production [55]. An assessment of MP impacts on the environment found that released MPs could have significant impacts on the potential loss of species diversity [56], which aligns with the conclusion of our study, where environmental effects are based on physical effects on biota. When performing such comparisons, it is important to note that LCA results among different studies are highly variable based on the selected system boundaries, impact assessment methods, and considered data variables.

The results of this study provide an opportunity to recommend best practices in the short-, medium-, and long-term regarding wastewater treatment for industrial processes and management of final MP waste. The collection of MP waste, which allows for water reuse, is a viable short-term solution for industrial practice. However, industries should look towards truly circular solutions in the medium term, which would allow for the reuse of purified water, as well as sustainable reuse of collected waste. In the long-term, considerations should be made towards energy optimization and utilization of sustainable materials to carry out the treatment process to avoid burdening the environment while removing MP waste from wastewater.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrated both the removal effectiveness and environmental benefits of a novel agglomeration–fixation process using organosilanes for MP and COD removal in industrial wastewater treatment by deploying a water treatment system on a pilot plant scale. Wastewater treatment sustainability was showcased through a holistic evaluation of removal capabilities and waste reuse potential, where pilot trials were complemented by

LCAs of the entire system, based on three separate scenarios: (1) the status quo with no direct treatment of industrial wastewater flowing to the municipal WWTP, (2) the pilot plant system operating in semi-continuous batches, and (3) an optimized continuous process which makes key substitutions to lessen environmental burdens and shows the benefits of MP waste reuse as concrete filler.

The pilot trials showed remarkable removal efficiencies, with COD reduction averaging 96% and MPs being removed by $98.0 \pm 1.1\%$ by mass and 100% by particle count. These results underscore the potential of this technology for significant improvements in wastewater quality. When comparing the pilot plant to the optimized circular system, the latter showed substantial environmental impact reductions across the evaluated impact categories, where, e.g., global warming potential was reduced by over 96%. The reduced consumption of filter fleece through the use of an endless belt filter contributed greatly to these environmental benefits, with the combined setup demonstrating a potential advancement in sustainable wastewater treatment.

Comparative analysis showed notable differences in end-of-life strategies when dealing with removed MP waste. The incineration of plastic waste remains a common practice for the final treatment of MPs, however, its recycling and reuse have shown to be the way forward for a circular economy and to contribute towards resource conservation and environmental protection. Extending the life cycle of MPs through their reuse as filler material presents unburdening benefits provided by the avoidance of new raw material extraction. Additionally, the results for impact categories related to human toxicity and ecotoxicity show that eliminating emissions from incineration is a key aspect of impact reduction. In this way, the study also highlighted the importance of LCAs in evaluating the environmental performance of novel wastewater treatment technologies with circular economy principles.

The study contains certain limitations with regard to dataset availability for the modeling of certain flows within the LCA. Whenever specific data for Germany were unavailable, geographical boundaries were defined for the area of Europe. It should also be noted that the quantification methodology for life cycle impacts for MP release into the environment is still in its early stages of development. Future work should address the impacts of MP release on ecosystems and human health, as well as focus on the potential for energy optimization of wastewater treatment systems, particularly since electricity demand was shown to be the main driver of impacts, even for the optimized process. Additionally, comparative assessments should be made between various methods of MP removal, assessing the sustainability of novel methods in comparison to conventional treatment.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/w17050671/s1>, Table S1: Measured and assumed values for the calculation of the yearly removal performance of the pilot plant. And Figure S1: Breakdown of individual process impacts on evaluated impact categories: (a) abiotic depletion, (b) abiotic depletion of fossil fuels, (c) acidification, (d) eutrophication, (e) freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, (f) human toxicity, (g) marine aquatic ecotoxicity, (h) ozone layer depletion, (i) photochemical oxidation, (j) terrestrial ecotoxicity.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

COD	Chemical oxygen demand
GAC	Granular activated carbon
GWP	Global warming potential
IBC	Intermediate bulk container
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
MP	Microplastic
PAFs	Potentially affected fraction of species
TEOS	Tetraethylorthosilicate
TSSs	Total suspended solids
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

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